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Ezh2 control of autoimmunity.

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We describe an immunogenic program controlled by Ezh2. The program contained genes encoding receptors for lipid inflammatory mediators (CYSLTR1), innate immune sensors (STING1), the IBD regulatory cytokine IL-23, and *NFAT5*. These genes in the immunogenic program were largely strictly controlled by a non-canonical function of Ezh2 associated with degradation of Ezh2, as a classical inhibitor of the SET methyltransferase domain of Ezh2 (C24) was similar to wild-type in program expression and left immunogenic program genes unaffected. In primary human erythroid cells, Ezh2 controlled the expression of cGAS.

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